

FOOD ALLERGY IN CHILDREN

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Relevance. Gastrointestinal food allergy is an important medical and social problem. Data on the prevalence of this pathology are very contradictory. Thus, according to a number of researchers, at least 20-30% of the population are convinced that they have some form of food allergy. According to epidemiological studies, the prevalence of proven food allergies in developed countries among children in the first year of life is 6%-8%, among adolescent children - 2%-4%, and among adults - 1.5%.

Purpose of the study: To study the health status of preschool children with gastrointestinal food allergies, to develop effective criteria for the diagnosis and prevention of exacerbations of this disease.

Materials and methods of research. Design, Setting, and Participants: Participants in the Child to Adult Development Study, an epidemiological cohort of 57 children and adolescents recruited in 2022 from health and education settings that provided services to children with a history of allergies, ages 5 to 12 years. in 6 rural places and in the city of Bukhara.

Results of the study: The health status of preschool children with gastrointestinal food allergies is characterized by a high frequency of concomitant pathologies (allergic diseases predominated 69.0%, nervous system pathology 52.6%), intrauterine infections 35.2%, ENT diseases 29.8%), severity of pain syndrome (in 78.5%), frequent formation of intestinal syndrome (in 82.5%). For these patients, symptoms of general intoxication are typical, in 56.1% of cases - skin manifestations of allergies. The immune status of preschool children with gastrointestinal food allergies is characterized by an increased level of 1E in 41.2% of cases, a high content of allergens specific to wheat flour, cow's milk, dairy products and chicken eggs. Changes in the humoral, cellular and phagocytic components of immunity are multidirectional. High values of O-antibodies to gliadin with normal levels of 1 α A-antibodies and antibodies to tissue transglutaminase allow us to reject the diagnosis of celiac disease in children with gastrointestinal food allergies.

Conclusion

Among children with gastrointestinal food allergies, there were almost equal numbers of boys and girls. Boys made up 49.1%, girls - 50.9%. The age composition was as follows: from 1 to 3 years - 35 people (61.4%), from 4 to 5 years - 17 people (29.8%) and from 6 to 7 years - 5 people (8.8%).

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